

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Roy**FIRST NAME:** Tonya**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** DR. GULMA**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote references (with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

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QUIZ FOR ACA-401D PERIOD 6

1. The five elements of any argument are just answers to the kinds of questions asked every day. These questions must be asked on the reader's behalf. What are these five elements?

- Claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgment and response, warrant.¹**
- Claim, hypothesis, research, acknowledgment and response, objections.
- Hypothesis, reason, evidence, reason for argument, warrant.
- Claim, reason, research, alternative points of view, relevance.

2. What is the definition of a warrant?

¹ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

It states a general principle based on our experiences in the world: when a certain general condition exists, we're justified in saying that a certain general consequence regularly follows.²

A statement that leads readers to accept a claim based on research.

All data on which you base your reasons.

Finding a question and imagining a tentative answer.

3. Secondary sources are used for three purposes:

To keep us updated on current research, find other points of view, and find models for your own research and analysis.³

To provide you with “raw” data or evidence you will use to develop, test, and ultimately justify your hypothesis or claim.

To give you a broad overview of your topic, assist you in making a scholarly argument, and synthesize other sources.

To obtain data through observation, assist with collecting data from original research, and keep up with the other research.

4. How good a research question is depends on its significance to some community of readers. Exactly what community depends on various factors. It is important to note that not all questions are equally good, but there are two wrong choices when

² Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 62.

³ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 36.

formulating a research question. Which of the choices below lists these two wrong choices?

- Trying to interest everyone and not trying to interest anyone at all.**⁴
- Choosing a question that has no interest to the writer but is attractive to some community of readers.
- Not being able to explain the significance of the research, but the writer has an interest in and knowledge of it.
- Readers can imagine writers conversing with one another, which raises several more questions.

5. To accept a claim, readers must accept the following:

- The warrant is true, the specific reason is true, the specific reason is a valid instance of the general condition side of the warrant, the specific claim is a valid instance of the general consequence side of the warrant, and no limiting conditions keep the warrant from applying.**⁵
- The hypothesis is stated, the claim is relevant, and the warrant may not be true.
- The specific reason is a valid instance of the general condition side of the warrant, and the specific claim is a valid instance of the general consequence of the warrant, and there may be some limiting conditions that keep the warrant from applying.
- No stated limitations or exceptions apply.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 21.

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 65.

6. Conducting dissertation research involves preparing two to four documents. Ideally, students prepare the following four dissertation documents:

The dissertation concept paper, the dissertation prospectus, the dissertation, and the dissertation manuscript.⁶

The dissertation concept paper, the dissertation prospectus, the compilation of all notes used to write the dissertation, and the dissertation manuscript.

The title of the dissertation, the dissertation concept paper, all collaboration of research, and the dissertation.

Completion of a systematic literature review results, establishing and executing the procedures for the dissertation, data analysis, and the dissertation.

7. What types of measures would you see typically used in qualitative research?

Questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, ratings of written, visual, auditory, or tactile exercises, observations, and documents or computer files of written, visual, or auditory data.⁷

Correspondence, the measure's quality, and the relevant measures to the variables.

Instruments, tests, questionnaires, interviews, ratings of written, visual, auditory, or tactile exercises, unobtrusive observations, and analysis of archival data.

The statement of purpose, the development of the measure, scales and subscales, standardization, and reliability.

⁶ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017) 2-7.

⁷ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 37.

8. What is the definition of content validity?

- To provide evidence that the content of the measures is congruent with the conceptual or theoretical basis of the instrument, test, questionnaire, structured interview, semi-structured interview, focus group, journal, written, visual, auditory, or tactile exercise, or observation.⁸**
- Documentation of the evidence that the measures' total, content, or factor-derived scale scores are not associated with measures of dissimilar constructs in a theoretically consistent direction.
- Documentation of the evidence that clusters of empirically associated items can be identified and reproduced across norm groups in a manner consistent with the measure's conceptual or theoretical basis.
- To provide evidence of the extent to which the total score, content score, or factor-derived scale scores of the measure accurately discriminate between groups of people.

9. Which sentence is correct using the apostrophe?

- The children's play area is next to the men's toilet.⁹**
- St. Michael's splits into Stewardson and McClellan Roads.
- I trust all the MP's.
- Music was lively in the 1970's.

⁸ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 40–41.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 16–17.

10. What is a true statement about EUCLID? (Choose one)

- EUCLID is an international intergovernmental organization with a university charter mandate under international law.¹⁰**
- EUCLID is an international intergovernmental organization with a university charter mandate under national law.
- EUCLID is a university that was formally established in 2003 based on the programs developed by the Euclid Consortium between 2002 and 2007.
- At EUCLID, the doctorate corresponds to 150 ECTS beyond Master 2, with a maximum of 180 ECTS for the thesis.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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¹⁰ EUCLID, *International and Academic Standard Applicable to the Programs of EUCLID (Pole Universitaire Euclide)* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2021), 2.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.